

MY PROFESSION IS AN AUTO MECHANIC

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6559873>

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Annotation: *The article discusses the history of the appearance of the car and the emergence of the profession of an auto mechanic. It also talks about the role of the auto mechanic profession and its relevance in the future.*

Keywords: *professions, auto mechanics, production of automobiles*

There is a huge variety of professions: doctor, journalist, engineer, veterinarian and others. I decided a long time ago what I want to become, and my choice is the profession of an auto mechanic. All my life I have been interested in how any technique works, how its mechanisms work. That is why I chose this profession. The history of the automotive industry in a short period of time, only about 100 years, has shown that it is very bright and fleeting, and we can only imagine what a car will look like in 100 years. The first auto mechanics appeared in the middle of the 18th century in countries where vehicles capable of moving independently appeared first. Since then, self-propelled mechanisms have constantly changed and improved. But any mechanism needs timely maintenance and repair, so specially trained people who are well versed in the car's structure were required. Thus, was born the profession of auto mechanic.

The profession originated in the distant 18th century with the advent of the first vehicles that had the ability to move independently. Such mechanisms often failed and needed people who knew the features of their device, who knew how to troubleshoot. The profession received more massive development in the 30s of the twentieth century. During this period of time, the rapid growth of motorists begins, and demand increases accordingly. This is due not only to the need for transportation, but rather to the invention of the first assembly line by Henry Ford. This led to the mass production of automobiles. The profession developed rapidly. The complication of car design in the 1950s gave impetus to the emergence of a profession with a narrower specialization. An auto mechanic is one of the most sought-after and highly paid professions today.

A car mechanic, or, as they say, a car mechanic, is a person who repairs cars. In doing so, his responsibilities include: - problem diagnosis; - search for a suitable way to solve it; - to work on its elimination. And, it would seem, this is all clear. But working as an auto mechanic comes with many pitfalls. In particular, a wide variety of equipment with which you have to deal. After all, now the market is overflowing with a huge number of both domestic and foreign car models, the structure of which varies greatly, and this complicates the work. In the modern world, the profession of auto mechanic is very much in demand. Thanks to the work of an auto mechanic, the service life of the car is significantly increased, which in turn reduces the risk of traffic accidents and ensures the safety of the driver on the road. An auto mechanic is a profession in which you need to skillfully operate with existing knowledge. This requires an analytical mind and an excellent memory. From the very beginning of training, I tried to master all the subtleties of this business, to remember the finest features of the car's design, its possible breakdowns and how to determine them. Due to the specifics of the profession, an auto mechanic often has to work with heavy parts. They need to be carried from place to place, lifted and held in a certain position. Therefore, strength and endurance are very important for the auto mechanic profession. There are many directions in this profession, but they are not so common and are needed only in specialized factories and in some workshops. Despite the fact that today the profession of an auto mechanic is quite common, it is still in demand and popular. There are auto repair shops that specialize both in complex repairs and in its individual types: painting, tuning, power supply repair, and so on. I got my first work experience during an internship at a technical school. Competence included knowledge of the following main automotive components and assemblies: - Engine management system - Suspension and steering - Electrical and electronic systems - Engine repair - Gearbox repair.

As a result of participation, I gained a huge experience in practical activities. I had the opportunity to demonstrate my knowledge and skills on the principles of operation of all vehicle systems, troubleshooting, repair and maintenance. Having taken part in the championship, I realized that my choice was still the right one, because I am happy to complete any practical task. As in any other profession, the most important criterion for hiring is the qualifications and experience of the employee. Therefore, auto mechanics are constantly improving their knowledge and skills. So, a person with the necessary knowledge and experience will always be able to find a job as an auto mechanic. And besides, this specialty is considered highly paid, which is also very nice. Over the years, car sales have been steadily growing, which means that the relevance of this profession will definitely not decrease in the near future. But the requirements for specialists of this profile are getting higher and higher every year, because progress does not stand still, and, consequently, car designs are becoming more complicated all the time.

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